

Overview of behavioral, economic and institutional barriers to implementation of energy efficiency in the Hellenic building sector

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Abstract

According to EUROSTAT and the Hellenic Statistical Authority, the building sector (residential and tertiary) is among the most energy intensive sectors in Hellas. The energy saving potential in this sector is significant, but the largest part of it is still unexploited.

The penetration of energy efficiency technologies and practices is influenced by the behavior of the consumers, such as public servants, household owners, tenants and SMEs owners, among others. Their decision is determined by information/awareness, costs, plus behavioral factors. In Hellas, the information and data about the attitude of consumers towards the established energy efficiency policy instruments, technologies and practices is limited.

The paper presents the sector-specific mapping and analysis of behavioral, economic and institutional barriers to the implementation of energy efficiency in two governance levels (national and local/regional) through a literature review based on project and survey results, national, European and international official reports. In the national level, most of the official reports, funded research projects and published research papers are addressing the households, the public sector and the hotels. In the local/regional level, the barriers are mostly linked with the initiative of Covenant of Mayors and the implementation of SEAPs.

1. Introduction

The building sector is among the most energy and carbon intensive sectors in EU. It accounts for 40% of the energy consumption and for 36% of the CO₂ emissions¹¹⁸. The promotion of Energy Efficiency (EE) is expected to reduce these trends, mainly through two key EU Directives, the Directive

about the Energy Performance of Buildings (2010/31/EU) and the Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU).

Furthermore EE will contribute to the European Union's (EU) energy security and its transition to a competitive low carbon economy (COM (2014) 520 final/23.07.2014¹¹⁹).

¹¹⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/buildings>

¹¹⁹ COM(2014) 520 final/23.07.2014. "Energy Efficiency and its contribution to energy security and the

2030 Framework for climate and energy policy". Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/2014_eec_communication_adopted_0.pdf

Table 1: EU energy and climate targets.

Year	Targets
2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ 20% cut in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (from 1990 levels) ▶ 20% of energy from renewables ▶ 20% improvement in energy efficiency
2030	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ 40% cut in GHG emissions (from 1990 levels) ▶ at least a 27% share of renewable energy consumption ▶ at least 27% energy savings compared with the business-as-usual scenario
2050	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ 80% cut in GHG emissions (from 1990 levels)

The EU targets for energy and climate change, presented at table 1, include also those for the improvement of EE.

Despite the undertaken measures for supporting EE investments, according to a European Commission analysis¹²⁰, a shortfall of 1%-2% in relation to the 20% target is expected in year 2020. This is partly related to the “energy efficiency gap” which refers to the failure of consumers to make cost-effective EE investments. In this context, the policies should be modified so as to reflect the end-user’s behavior. Therefore, the policy makers will face new challenges in performing scenario analysis of the different EE policies by explicitly linking behavioral anomalies of the end-user to EE investments (Gillingham K. et al., 2013).

The end-user’s behavior that influence both the purchase of equipment and the use of energy is determined by information/awareness, energy costs, plus social, educational and cultural factors (WBCSD, 2008). Consequently, there are barriers for the implementation of EE policies and technologies that are related to the aforementioned factors.

This paper presents the sector-specific mapping and analysis of behavioral, economic and institutional barriers to the implementation of EE in two governance levels (national and local/regional) through literature review. It is structured as follows: the first section refers to the Hellenic building sector, the second section refers to the behavioral, economic and institutional barriers that were mapped in this sector

concerning EE technologies and policies and the third section presents the conclusions of the overview.

2. Hellenic building sector

The final energy consumption for the Hellenic building sector was 17,129 Mtoe in 2012, representing the highest energy consumption with 45% (residential and tertiary), along with the transport sector which had 37% (YPEKA, 2014).

Households account for 84% of the total building stock (72% of total surface) (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). From the remaining 16%, 3,62% corresponds to offices, stores, educational buildings, hospitals and hotels (Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2014). Table 2 reflects the situation according to the 2011 census (YPEKA, 2014).

At national level, the Hellenic EE policy package for this sector includes a variety of policy instruments (regulatory, financial, dissemination, awareness and capacity building), Action Plans, Programmes and Initiatives, most of which derived from the transposition of EU Directives into the national laws. More specifically (Konidari P. et al., 2015):

- Regulatory policy instruments: Energy labeling, energy audits, Regulation for Energy Performance of Buildings – Minimum requirements of energy performance for buildings, metering, energy auditors, eco-design requirements, energy management systems;

¹²⁰ COM(2014) 520 final/23.07.2014

Table 2: Number of buildings by type (2011 census) (YPEKA, 2014).

Type	Number
Households	4.122.088
Hotels	8.309
Schools & educational centers	15.576
Offices & shops	152.550
Hospital & medical centers	1.742
Other	625.630
Total	4.925.895

- Dissemination and awareness instruments/informative policy instruments: energy performance certificate; Green Public Procurements, Voluntary agreements; information campaigns for certain programmes such as “Energy Efficiency at Household buildings”;
- Economic policy instruments: taxation on energy products and electricity, Green Fund-subsidies, financial incentives (subsidies, financial exemptions), financial incentives for replacement of devices/systems;
- Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services: ESCO market promotion.

At local level, most of the EE policies are linked with the European Initiative “Covenant of Mayors”¹²¹, which involves local and regional authorities that are voluntarily committing to increase EE and use of RES. One hundred ten (110) Hellenic municipalities are signatories of the Covenant, seventy-nine (79) of which have submitted their Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP) and four (4) of which have already been at the stage of the results monitoring.

3. Barriers

A literature review was conducted using recent project and survey results, national, European and international official reports and published research papers, seeking for behavioral, economic and institutional barriers to the promotion of EE in the Hellenic

building sector. The following analysis includes barriers that: i) were identified by the majority of the used for this paper references/different sources, ii) cover broader spectrum of technologies or practices and iii) were observed both in national and local level.

a. Behavioral barriers

The following behavioral barriers were identified based on the literature review.

Low level of environmental awareness

The Hellenic society is not yet sensitive enough towards environment, sustainability and energy conservation (Karkanian C. et al., 2010; Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Low level of awareness regarding the environmental, economical, EE benefits and the concept of “sustainable and energy efficient building” influence greatly the energy refurbishment policies (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Research studies for certain regions in the country highlighted the fundamental role of energy awareness, combined with targeted information on technical and cost issues (Zografakis N. et al., 2012). More specifically:

- A research on low income households in the Kastoria prefecture regarding the use of energy saving practices showed that only one third of them select “A” energy class electrical devices and one quarter use energy efficient lamps (Christidou C. et al., 2014).
- In Crete, a survey that included 685 companies showed that only 9,8% were using Inverter technology of air-

¹²¹ http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/index_en.html

conditioning split units (Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012).

Limited information for EE generally

This barrier is closely linked with the previous one. According to the Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy, consumers usually have insufficient information and education on the rational use of energy, leading to (YPEKA, 2010):

- installation of individual air-conditioning systems without technical study;
- use of poor performance devices;
- non maintenance of the heating system.

The Ministry attempted to confront this barrier with the “Energy Efficiency at Household Buildings” Program (YPEKA, 2010).

Incomplete or no information obstructs the use of cost-effective and energy-efficient technologies. The lack of readily available information and demonstration increases the investment costs for such technologies due to: increased search costs; increased investment uncertainty. In Hellas, empirical evidence was gathered with the use of questionnaires and face-to-face interviews during 2004 (Kounetas K. et al., 2011).

The same barrier is observed on hotel owners (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). There is low awareness for the costs and benefits of EE and RES technologies (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). It would be useful if they were informed about: i) appropriate technologies that could be applied in the different operating areas of the hotel such as restaurants, bedrooms, etc. (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011), and ii) the policy framework or good practices from other countries (Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).

Furthermore, there is lack of information among public servants and citizens regarding the energy consumption of the public institutes (CERTus, 2015). At local level, the financial instruments that could be used for the implementation of SEAPs were not known to most cities administrations (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).

Incomplete and/or limited information for emerging innovative technologies

The European Commission identified a number of potential barriers for Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and consumers

in building sectors in EU Member States regarding the access to and the spread of EE technologies (Kounetas K. et al., 2011). This barrier is observed in SMEs mainly because of the limited availability of information, resulting from the limited resources compared to larger firms. Nevertheless, the argument that the level of information is technology specific is supported (Kounetas K. et al., 2011).

Aloofness due to negative past experience

Negative experiences are frequently observed in Europe (ENTRANZE, 2014). They are characterized either as fading (such as early not-so-convincing demonstrations of solar thermal systems and ground source heat pumps) or more persistent (such as opposition to mechanical ventilation - prerequisite for heat recovery; quality problems in thermal renovations; underperformance of air source heat pumps). These are observed for solutions which are still at initial stage and there are not enough relevant good examples and known experiences (ENTRANZE, 2014). There is also fear for still unknown technologies (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012).

Habits and living styles (comfort)

Working habits are very strong. Office equipment such as computers, automated teller machines, faxes and digital video recorders DVRs are usually on stand-by mode during the working hours due to heavy work pressure (Spyropoulos N. G., Balaras A. C., 2011). Consequently, potential energy savings in working buildings/spaces were not considered under the requirements of the Energy Performance of Buildings (Law 3661/2008 – Common Ministerial Decision 5825/9.4.2010) (Spyropoulos N. G., Balaras A. C., 2011). The hoteliers believe that high energy use is necessary to ensure the comfort of guests (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011).

Diverse socio-economic background & multilateral ownership

In Hellas, there are usually multi-family buildings with more than 10 apartment owners, leading to a mosaic of rarely converging opinions towards building renovation (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014; Theodoridou I. et al., 2012; ENTRANZE, 2014). Furthermore, difficulties for the decision on renovation are attributed to the

different socio-economic background (Gelegenis J. et al., 2014).

Unwillingness to go beyond the minimum requirements

EE standards in building codes rarely refer to the optimal standards. Also, building owners and particularly hotel owners are unwilling to make EE interventions that go beyond the minimum requirements, established in building codes (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). Additionally, builders and designers are rarely motivated to go beyond the required EE standards, even more if such efforts will increase initial costs (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011).

The aforementioned barriers are summarized in table 3.

b. Economic barriers

The literature review concluded to the following behavioral barriers.

Economic recession

It is one of the main economic barriers for supporting EE investments and policies at national and local level since it resulted in:

- limited resources and interest to provide loans from the side of banks, particularly for the deep renovation of public buildings towards nearly zero energy consumption which have big payback period (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012; CERtus, 2015); The bank loans in Hellas were significantly contracted, leading to a subsequent reduction of investments on building renovations. Indicatively, according to the latest data from the Bank of Greece, the net flow of credit to households was recorded negative from April 2010 and was estimated to reduce 202 million Euros in August 2014, while the growth rate of mortgage loans was at – 3,0% (YPEKA, 2014).
- poor loan capability of private investors (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). The liquidity problems of the Hellenic businesses and banks hindered the implementation of the JESSICA initiative (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012).
- income decrease and change of consumption patterns of the population in the recent years, that put aside investments for energy renovations (YPEKA, 2014).

Table 3: Behavioral barriers in the Hellenic building sector.

Title	Related policy or technology	Type of subsectors & consumers
Low level of environmental awareness	Refurbishment, energy saving lamps, appliances “A”, inverter technology air-condition	Residential and Tertiary: residents and shop owners, hotel owners
Limited information for EE generally	Refurbishment, bio-climatic design, heating & air-conditioning systems, SEAPs	Residential and Tertiary: residents, public servants, and private company owners (such as hotels)
Incomplete and/or limited information for emerging innovative technologies	EE technologies	Residential and Tertiary: residents, public servants, and SMEs owners
Aloofness due to negative past experience	EE solutions at initial stage (eg. air-source heat pumps)	Residential and Tertiary
Diverse socio-economic background	Refurbishment	Multi-family households
Multilateral ownership	Refurbishment, thermal renovation	Residential and Tertiary: Apartment buildings/Blocks
Habits and living styles (comfort)	Refurbishment, stand-by mode of appliances	Residential and Tertiary
Unwillingness to go beyond the minimum requirements	EE solutions	Tertiary: mainly hotels

- limited national subsidies (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Despite the level of communication and the visibility of efforts for a programme/initiative in the media and in different communities, economic-based initiatives require substantial support from the government (CRISP project, 2012).
- important national budget cuts. For instance, this was the case of Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRESS) which is the national institute responsible for the promotion of EE and RES (Energy Efficiency Watch, 2013). Also, at local level, EE and RES investments through SEAPs were endangered due to budget cuts. Indicatively, Hellenic cities were succumbed to 40% cut from the government (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).

Costly innovative technologies

Innovative technologies, especially those of Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB)(recent EU Directive) are still new for the market and costly, for instance solar cooling (CERTus, 2015).

In the public sector, the technical staff of the public buildings is reluctant to approve and proceed with the installation of new and innovative technologies, since there is lack of actual successful examples (CERTus, 2015).

Reluctance for investments with long payback period

The payback period of EE interventions is usually quite great (YPEKA, 2014). Some of the EE options are considered rather expensive making them of no practical interest from the point of market acceptability, particularly without any financial support, subsidies or other financial instruments (Droutsas K.G. et al., 2014). EE investments with long payback periods (more than 10 years), are characterized as unattractive (INTERREG IVC, 2014).

Building owners that rent their offices/apartments do not apply EE interventions such as installation of double-glazing windows due to the increased capital cost (Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012). On the other hand, tenants are discouraged to

undertake such actions that go beyond the purchase of EE appliances, due to the long payback period and their temporary stay in the building (Tsagarakis P.K. et al., 2012).

An indicative example is the case of green roofs in Greece (Green roofs were supported by recent law and the national programme “Green roofs in public buildings” (refurbishment of buildings) that was launched in 2011). People were discouraged to proceed with the installation of green roofs due to the high initial investment (CRISP project, 2012).

Also at local level, the municipalities prefer investments with a payback period equal to their tenure of local administration (five years), since this period coincides with the financial planning. In any case they avoid making investments with a payback period more than 10 years (CERTus, 2015). For public schools, EE interventions that were cost effective and with very small payback periods were preferred by the school administration (such as: replacement of oil boilers with natural gas ones, thermal insulation of the hot water distribution pipes in the older buildings) (Dascalaki G. E., Sermpezoglou G. V., 2011).

Still developing market for energy services

Currently, the Hellenic EE market lags behind those of other EU countries. The market for energy services (especially for the refurbishment of buildings towards NZEBs) is still developing. The access for all consumers and market players to integrated and highly qualitative energy services shows high potential for future growth in EE and will be a key priority for Greece's energy policy (RePublic ZEB project, 2015). The following barriers were identified (YPEKA, 2014):

- Lack of adequate renovations' supply chain service;
- Lack of energy labeling, energy standards and certification in construction materials;
- Lack of technical support and reliability of energy services;
- Lack of metering / direct mechanisms (such as smart meters) for the monitoring of energy savings due to renovation.

Limited financial incentives

State support for energy renovations and renewable heating and cooling systems appears to be lower in Greece than in similar south European countries (Italy and Spain) (ENTRANZE, 2014).

For the programme EXOIKONOMO (Energy Saving), the available budget was considered insufficient for the implementation of integrated EE plans that will cover the overall needs of municipalities (target group) (Remaco SA, 2010). This barrier could be overcome with the institutionalization of energy services contracts and third party financing (Remaco SA, 2010).

There is absence of incentives for the implementation of bioclimatic design (Karkanias C., 2010). Contractors have a negative attitude towards the adoption of EE technologies or practices such as the bioclimatic architecture, due to the use of costly building materials and the installation of passive energy systems, that results in smaller selling profit for them (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). The profit from designing and constructing a conventional building requires less time and reaches up to 160% of the construction cost, while the profit for the bioclimatic buildings is much smaller (Karkanias C. et al., 2010).

The majority of hotels face difficulties in getting financing for any types of investments (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). Due to their poor credit ratings, small- and medium- size hotels often serve costlier loans than the large or chain hotels (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011). So, easier access to finance at viable interest rates is needed for most hotels so as to implement EE and RES technology investments, maybe through the development of innovative financial packages with low interest loans and/or performance guarantees (Hotel Energy Solutions, 2011).

Rebound effect

High income inhabitants live usually in relatively new buildings that show improved energy performance. Indicatively, only 8% of low income households live at buildings with isolation and double glazing windows, while the respective percentage for high income households is 64% (Association of Greek Contracting Companies, 2008). The

improvement in the energy performance of the building's envelope and of heating system- as part of the EE measure of refurbishment of residential buildings - is being offset by the higher living and comfort standards of those inhabitants leading to higher energy consumption. It is representative that the very low income households have almost the same energy consumption for heating needs with the very high income households (Association of Greek Contracting Companies, 2008).

Hidden costs

There are hidden costs for the implementation of EE interventions apart from the net costs of the interventions themselves, such as management fees and other.

An indicative example was the JESSICA initiative, where significant management fees of the European Investment Bank led to the renegotiation of the financing agreement with commercial banks and the management fee was reduced to 1,2%, from the initially planned 1,9% (Tsipouri L. and Athanassopoulou S., 2012).

Also, it is difficult and time consuming for the municipality services to monitor and to be consistent with the legislation (for energy efficiency and particularly for the forthcoming new Directive concerning the nearly zero energy consumption) (CERTus, 2015). Particularly for public buildings there are numerous legislative and regulatory provisions that determine the procedure to conclude in study contracts and / or construction renovation projects (CERTus, 2015). The payment procedure for contracts (i.e. registration at the budget, credit commitment, decision of undertaking, etc) is very complicated and time consuming resulting to delays of payments and consequently to delay of works (CERTus, 2015).

The aforementioned barriers are summarized in the Table 4.

c. Institutional barriers

Lack of targeted legislation

According to the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, the lack of relevant legislation for the past 30 years resulted in failure of integration of modern

technologies in buildings, leading to (YPEKA, 2010):

- partial or total lack of insulation;
- obsolete frames;
- lack of sun protection of the southern and western sides;
- insufficient use of the high solar potential of the country;
- inadequate maintenance of heating / air-conditioning resulting to poor performance.

There is also still no defined national standard for conducting adequate and confirmed measurements regarding actual energy consumption in buildings (YPEKA, 2014).

Hellas has not yet defined the levels of nearly zero energy consumption according to EU Directive 2012/27/EC (CERTus, 2015).

Also, hoteliers do not adopt EE technologies or practices due to the lack of effective national policy in the sector of tourism (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015). This barrier along with the voluntary approach in which EE is pursued, set energy audits and reporting on the hotel environmental performance as a necessary initial step that will facilitate policymaking on EE (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015).

Tenure status

Hellas has a very large tenure quota, mainly for apartments, which can greatly

influence the implementation of retrofitting measures (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012). Due to multiple ownerships, there is low implementation or even rejection of energy refurbishment measures (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012).

Unlike in the case of the Energy Building Certificate, the owners of an apartment in a multi-family building are not legally bound to proceed to retrofitting interventions (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012).

Consequently, if such interventions can be implemented partially, then the concerned party/owner can act on its will (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012).

But when the retrofitting measures concern the whole building, the legal framework is not clear giving the following options (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012): i) according to the statute, the respective works are in force or simple majority could be demanded, ii) if one or more owners disagree to contribute to the respective costs, then the legal procedure for the “res judicata” could last even up to 3 years. Consequently, many owners avoid investing in energy upgrade. So there is a need for the revision of this legal framework. A suggestion would be to configure the property pricing according to the energy performance characteristics, under a specific legal framework (Theodoridou I. et al., 2012).

Table 4: Economic barriers in the Hellenic building sector.

Title	Related policy or technology	Type of subsectors & consumers
Economic recession	EE solutions, NZEBs, SEAPs	Residential and Tertiary
Costly innovative technologies	EE and NZEB technologies such as solar cooling	Residential and Tertiary
Reluctance for investments with long payback period	Refurbishment, EE solutions such as green roofs, SEAPs	Residential and Tertiary
Still developing market for energy services	Refurbishment, construction materials	Residential and Tertiary
Limited financial incentives	EE solutions, bio-climatic design, SEAPs	Residential and Tertiary: residents, small-medium sized hotel owners
Rebound effect	Refurbishment	Residential: high income owners
Hidden costs	EE investments	Tertiary: SMEs

The person who decides for the EE level of a building does not coincide with the person who bears the cost of energy consumption therein (e.g. the cost for the energy upgrade of a building under lease burdens the owner but the benefit from the energy savings is attributed to the lessee), known also as split incentives (YPEKA, 2014).

Complex administrative procedures

Legislation and procedures concerning EE in buildings (i.e. in nZEB) are complex and puzzling for the public, due to lack of dissemination actions (ENTRANZE, 2014). In addition, the legislation on Energy Efficiency of the building stock is relatively recent - entered into force in 2010 - while during the last years, numerous amendments to existing legislation were made, accompanied by a considerable number of ministerial decisions and circulars (YPEKA, 2014).

Bureaucratic procedures that hindered the implementation of publicly funded projects were reported in the following cases:

- “Green Neighborhoods Programme”, whose objective was the energy renovation of a low-income neighborhood in the broad area of Athens (Greece), with the participation of unemployed inhabitants, recruited and trained as installers and maintainers of their building (Request 2 Action project, 2012);
- “Green Roofs” initiative (CRISP, 2012);
- “EXOIKONOMO KAT OIKON” programme: there were up to 6-month delays in issuing the appropriate building permits for EE interventions as required by national law (Remaco SA, 2010).

Hellas has not yet defined the different levels of nearly zero energy consumption based on the different use of buildings (CERTus, 2015). There are time delays in updating the necessary documents for the implementation of the respective legislation.

According to the new Direction of Energy Policy and Performance of the Ministry for Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy ¹²² (old name Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change), the respective regulation is expected to be published by the end of 2015 (CERTus, 2015). It is also expected that the levels of nearly zero energy consumption for the existing buildings, apart from the governmental ones, shall not be mandatory unless radical renovations are made (CERTus, 2015).

According to the findings of the European project CERTus, at municipality level, the legal framework based on which the municipality could award a contract with a company of energy services is not concrete (CERTus, 2015). It is also difficult and time consuming for the municipality staff to monitor and to be consistent with the legislation for EE (CERTus, 2015). Particularly for the public buildings, there are numerous legislative and regulatory provisions that concern the study contracts and / or construction renovation projects (CERTus, 2015).

- Apart from the defined procedure of assigning a contract (under the EU Directive 2012/27/EC), the legislation that describes the payment procedure (ie registration at the budget, credit commitment, decision of undertaking, etc.) is very complicated and time consuming resulting to delays of payments and consequently to delay of works (CERTus, 2015).
- The technical services are obliged to follow a difficult and time-consuming procedure for the approval of any study or work for renovation (CERTus, 2015). These lengthy processes often lead to non-implementation of interventions.

The legislation for the EU Directive 2012/27/EC foresees that the tariffication for the study and construction of any type of intervention in public buildings should be done according to the Analytical Tariffication of Construction Works (ATCW) which differs significantly from the actual market prices due

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<http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=230&language=el-GR>

to the lack of regular update of catalogues for material and works (CERtus, 2015). The last update of the ATCW took place in 2007 (CERtus, 2015). Consequently, the list of the Analytical Tariffication of Construction Works does not include innovative systems and materials (CERtus, 2015).

Ineffective urban and land planning / special building cases

Due to the lack of urban and land planning in Hellas during the last 30 years, the majority of new buildings have been constructed in a very dense urban space (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). Vertical tall buildings with narrow vents along the floors, without any thermal insulation in walls and roofs and with very few features of traditional Hellenic architecture, dominated the decades of 1960s and 1970s (Karkanias C., et al., 2010). These buildings generated serious operational problems such as insufficient lighting and poor ventilation, apart from the high energy consumption and the subsequent operational expenses (Karkanias C. et al., 2010). Due to the lack of wide streets, big sites, and exposed facades, that limit the utilization of sun, the implementation of bioclimatic architecture is difficult (Karnanias C. et al., 2010).

Additionally, the situation is worsened since there are historic, traditional or cultural heritage buildings in Hellas, where no changes in the facade are allowed (the refurbishment of such buildings need to follow specific rules). That is why external thermal insulation is often not allowed to be installed. Although the internal insulation does not interfere with the facade, the internal system leads to non-negligible loss of indoor space and is related to high risk of moisture condensation (Kolaitis D. I. et al., 2013).

Limited expertise and resources

This barrier was mainly identified at municipality level. Although the Covenant of Mayors includes simple procedures, the municipalities' staff did not have the required experience (Christoforidis et al., 2013). Also, researchers have quoted the inability of rural Hellenic communities to build suitable SEAPs, due to inadequate financial capacity and/or human resources (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Furthermore, they insist that there is

necessity for support to develop action plans and monitor SEAP's implementation.

Lack of detailed data

One of the considerable barriers in studying the energy performance and adopting energy efficiency technologies and practices in buildings is the lack of data and the diversion of management. The building users have no or incomplete information concerning the energy performance of their building, and consequently, they are not aware of how they can improve it (CERtus, 2015).

More specifically:

- At national level, the available data for Hellenic residential buildings is not sufficient so as to be used in building stock models or other relevant research studies (Dascalaki G. E. et al., 2011). There are data only for the insulation level (missing, partial or completely insulated) while there are no detailed reports on heat generation systems, domestic hot water or space heating systems, and no time series data are available for heat distribution systems (Dascalaki G. E. et al., 2011). The data gaps are attributed to the absence of systematic data collection (Dascalaki G. E. et al., 2011).
- In municipality buildings, the lack of a defined procedure or staff for the energy consumption monitoring hinders the collection of energy data or any relevant information (CERtus, 2015; ADVANCE, 2014). This problem will be most probably overcome by a legislative provision soon to be published by the Central Government and will concern the appointment of an energy manager in municipalities (CERtus, 2015).
- In public buildings and particularly in schools, the collection of data on the actual energy consumption is a difficult task because (Dimoudi A., Kostarela P., 2009): i) heating costs are covered by the school budget which is under the responsibility of the school committees, that usually change every year and in many cases do not keep relevant records. ii) electricity costs are covered by the municipality.

- In the hotel sector, the respective managers cannot provide data on the energy consumption of hotel facilities due to lack of an organized record (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015). This attitude underestimates the value of energy monitoring and consequently the implementation of sustainable policies (Pieri S. P. et al., 2015; Maleviti E. et al., 2012; 2011).

Limited coordination among the different governance levels

In many cases, mayors signed the “Covenant of Mayors” during their election period, but afterwards they proved to be unfamiliar with the existing financial instruments to develop and implement the SEAP and the energy efficiency actions (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Additionally, the majority of municipalities’ employees, along with citizens, were not informed about their mayor's initiative to sign the Covenant (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013). Consequently, there was substantially

low support for the preparation of SEAP from the side of employees, while the communities themselves had limited or even no information about the initiative and its possible benefits for their region (Christoforidis C. G. et al., 2013).

The aforementioned barriers are summarized in the Table 5.

4. Conclusions

Approximately twenty different barriers were identified regarding the end-users behavior mainly towards EE technologies and practices for the Hellenic building sector. These barriers are equally distributed in the three main categories behavioral, economic and institutional.

The information barrier was present in two of the three categories through the following barriers: Limited information for EE generally (behavioral), incomplete and/or limited information for emerging innovative technologies (behavioral), lack of detailed data (Institutional), limited expertise and resources (Institutional).

Table 5: Institutional barriers in the Hellenic building sector.

Title	Related policy or technology	Type of subsectors & consumers
Lack of targeted legislation	NZEBs, modern EE technologies and practices	Residential and Tertiary
Tenure status	Refurbishment	Residential and Tertiary
Complex administrative procedures	Refurbishment, SEAPs	Residential and Tertiary: mainly public buildings
Ineffective urban and land planning/special building cases	Bioclimatic design, refurbishment	Residential and Tertiary
Limited expertise and resources	Refurbishment, bioclimatic design, SEAPs	Residential and Tertiary
Lack of detailed data	Refurbishment, SEAPs	Residential and Tertiary: households, public buildings, hotels
Limited coordination among the different governance levels	SEAPs	Residential and Tertiary

Additionally, during the literature review it was concluded that the information and the data about end-user’s attitude to EE policy instruments, technologies and practices is limited. Consequently, the design of new adequate EE policy instruments needs to take into serious consideration the information barrier.

Although there are on-going socio-economic research efforts (studies, initiatives, programmes, dissemination actions) to overcome all these barriers (e.g. “Energy Efficiency at household buildings”), further research efforts are required for achieving the respective EU target for EE.

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